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Research Article

**A CONTEXTUAL ANALYSIS OF THE DISORDER IN THE
WEST CURRENT HISTORY**¹Dr Asad Waheed ul Zaman, ²Dr Saira Asghar, ³Dr Usama Javed¹Mayo Hospital Lahore²Nishtar Medical University and Hospital³Lahore General Hospital

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Abstract:

An 11-month-old child was brought to the emergency room with seizures and spasms, eye deviation to the left, fever and kicking. The history revealed that the underlying 2-month-old child was shocking but consoling and had an exaggerated alarm reflex. After several months, the mother whined that the child had spasms, that is, a deviation of the eye to the left side, a tonic development of the colon of the two upper appendages that lasted for one minute and went off as expected with a recurrence of 27 times a day at first and now with medication it has decreased to 8-10 times a day. The youngster was on: syp. Gardinal 3.7ml oral Od and Tab. Bexel 1\4 Tds. The mother's prenatal history was typical, it was an ordinary transport at term, however the infant did not cry long after birth and required prompting and aspiration to be inhaled. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from June 2018 to May 2019. By the third day of life, the infant created severe respiratory distress and was transferred to the neonatal intensive care unit where he was rescued for about fourteen days and then released. He was placed in a lower class family unit and was placed under selective supervision until the age of six months, at which time weaning began. There is no critical family ancestry and the child is vaccinated up to the age stipulated in the national immunization plan. The disease began to appear in young people from the age of several months and had a symptomatic western disorder, the conceivable reason for which was asphyxia at birth, which required stimulation and aspiration. The infant has all three types of seizures that occur all the time and, in addition, is shattered, but this is consoling and relapse is also present.

Key words: Contextual analysis, Disorder, History.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Asad Waheed ul Zaman,**
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INTRODUCTION:

West's disorder or West's disorder is an extraordinary to rare epilepsy problem in newborns. It is named after the English physician and specialist William James West (1793-1848) who lived in Ton bridge [1-3]. In 1841, he observed this type of epilepsy in his own child, James Edwin West (1840-1860), who was about five months old at the time. He distributes his observations logically in an article in "The Lancet". He named the seizure "Salaam Tics" at the time [4].

It is also known by other names like:

1. Generalized Flexion Epilepsy
2. Infantile Epileptic Encephalopathy
3. Infantile Myoclonic Encephalopathy
4. Jackknife Convulsions
5. Massive Myoclonic
6. Salaam Spams, also as Infantile Spasms.

DEFINITION:

Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from June 2018 to May 2019. By the third day of life, the infant created severe respiratory distress and was transferred to the neonatal intensive care unit where he was rescued for about fourteen days and then released. He was placed in a lower class family unit and was placed under selective supervision until the age of six months, at which time weaning began. West's disorder is a set of three of infantile adjustment of a python-monic conception of the EEG (called hypsarhythmia) and developmental relapse. Two of the three components must be close together [5].

Incidence:

The rate is about 1:3200 to 1:3500 of live births. Statistically, young men are necessarily more influenced than young women, at a ratio of about 1.3 to 1. In 2011, out of 10 young people influenced, crises appear simply because they are between three and twelve months old. In rare cases, crises may occur in the first month or between the second and fourth year.

CAUSES:

1. If a case presents, the disorder is referred to as a symptomatic Western disorder, as is the case with aggression as an indication of another problem.
2. In one-third of cases there is evidence of a significant organic problem which includes: microcephaly, cortical dysplasia, cerebral decline, bacterial meningitis, tuberous sclerosis, hematoma of the head, vascular contortion, neurometabolic diseases, inborn contamination (CMV), hypoglycemia, brain damage due to asphyxia or hypoxia at birth.
3. First time after inoculation against measles, mumps and rubella or tetanus, pertussis, diphtheria, poliomyelitis, hepatitis B and Hib.

4. Western Cryptogenic Disorder: when an immediate reason cannot be resolved and the child has other neurological problems.
5. In situations where different children within the same family develop it, where it occurs at a progressive age in young males, X chromosomal heredity.
6. Idiopathic Western Idiopathic Disorder: when the reason cannot be determined.

CLINICAL FEATURES

1. Seizures that can occur in newborns with West's disease fall into three categories, broadly known as juvenile seizures. In general, the following three types of seizures occur, while the 03 types normally occur simultaneously, they can also occur independently of each other.

(a) Lightning attacks: abrupt and extreme myoclonic spasms of the whole body or parts of the body in a fraction of a second and the legs are specifically arched.

(b) Head nodding assaults: attacks of the flexor muscles of the throat and neck in which the jaw line is broken erratically towards the chest or the head is pulled inwards.

(c) Salaam or knife attacks: an attack on the flexor muscles with a rapid forward rotation of the head and middle muscles and a simultaneous raising and tilting of the arms while bringing the hands incompletely together in front of the chest and a thrashing (this resembles the Oriental stylized Welcome Salaam from which it takes its name).

2. Irritability in youth

3. Regression of the improvement until it is treated.

MANAGEMENT

Unlike the different types of epilepsy, it is difficult to treat. The effectiveness of treatment depends on its early conclusion and brief treatment, but there is no guarantee. Treatment is based on

1. Etiological arrangement
2. Mental health status at the time of injury.

THE PHARMACOLOGICAL MANAGEMENT CONSISTS OF MEDICATIONS LIKE:

1. Prednisolone
2. ACTH
3. Vigabatrin (Sabril)
4. Topiramate
5. Lamotrigine
6. Levitracetam

Other treatment mode- The Ketogenic Diet which has shown to be effective in treating infantile spasms up to 70% of children having a 50% or more reduction in seizures.

NURSES ROLE

1. Observe for the request for the occasions (before, during and after)
2. Duration, starting time, opportunities to hasten, practices, developments with change of position implying everything.
3. Possible waking period for the state of consciousness, reusability, motor ability, sensations and memory of previous sensations.
4. Educate guardians and parents about illness, medications and symptoms by pressuring the care of the young person with the equivalent.
5. Parents should be informed of the precautionary measures to be taken for the youth with West's disease.

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